

This project has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101005985

Social network tools and procedures for developing entrepreneurial skills in PhD programmes

D6.2 (WP6): Report on monitoring the project developments

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Contributor(s): CIMNE, WEGEMT

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Document Information Table

Contract number:	723360
Project acronym:	prodPhD
Project coordinator:	CIMNE
Document Responsible Partner:	UC3M
Deliverable type:	Report
Document title:	Report on monitoring the project developments
Document ID:	D6.2
Dissemination level:	Public (PU)
Filename:	D6.2
Status:	First version

Authoring & Review

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D6.2, 'Report on monitoring the project developments', aims to monitor the mid-term progress of the prodPhD project. This deliverable monitors the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of the actions in each work package of the project and provides an overall assessment of the results of each pilot action. KPI monitoring was based on the descriptive and evaluative operationalization of the KPIs in D6.1. However, the KPIs were initially not assigned specifically to individual work packages; the monitoring was therefore divided into two dimensions. First, the individual work packages were monitored in terms of 'overall assessment', where the partners reported the objectives of the work package, partners involved, discrepancies between intended and actual impact, modifications of plan, and progress plan. Second, the KPIs corresponding to each work package were monitored by the leader of each work package in line with their operationalization in D6.1.

This mid-term monitoring of the progress of the prodPhD project shows that the implemented activities thus far meet their corresponding KPIs. In addition, this deliverable also provides an overall assessment of each Work Package (WP). Both the KPI monitoring and the overall assessment of each WP show the activities completed thus far meet their targets and, hence, the prodPhD project is on track to deliver optimal outcomes to meet its aims.

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1. INTRODUCTION

WP6 aims to ensure that the produced knowledge and outcomes are visible, meet high-quality standards, and have an impact. Although it monitors and assesses the project's overall impact, it particularly focuses on the results of the demonstration actions (WP5) and the project's dissemination activities (WP7). For this purpose, various KPIs were defined and operationalized in D6.1 for use in monitoring and evaluating the activities in WP5 and WP7. The first WP6 deliverable, D6.1, took as its starting point the preliminary list of KPIs that was initially proposed (available in the Grant Agreement). Development monitoring will focus on the outputs (activities, materials, software tools) and the overall impact generated by the project actions.

The KPIs were specifically developed to monitor the activities in WP5 and WP7. Therefore, in order to monitor and evaluate the developments in each phase of the project, monitoring and evaluation work was divided into two dimensions. First, an overall descriptive assessment of the developments is reported in terms of objectives, partners involved, discrepancies between intended and actual impact, modification of previously set plans, and progress plan. Second, after the KPIs are assigned to the WPs, an evaluation of the activities is reported in the light of the KPIs.

As a first mid-term assessment, this report evaluates the overall progress of each WP and its KPIs. It is important to note that some activities have been completed (e.g., WP1, WP2, and WP3), while others either are still ongoing or have yet to kick off. Therefore, this deliverable provides an overall assessment of each WP and monitors the KPIs of the entire project. In some cases (in WP5, WP6, and WP7, to be exact), KPI monitoring will be evaluated in the final-term assessment.

This document consists of two main chapters. First, Chapter 2 provides an overall assessment of each WP and reports the KPIs of some WPs. Chapter 3 then provides some concluding remarks. The last section provides the work cited.

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2. OVERALL ASSESSMENT AND KPI MONITORING

This chapter of the deliverable is dedicated to the overall assessment of the WPs and the monitoring of their KPIs. All partners provided a report assessing their WPs, and the KPIs were monitored in line with the protocols defined in D6.1 in order to evaluate progress, including a statement and explanation of the current status of development, success of implementation, and performance.

2.1. Process. Development and performance

2.1.1. Work Package 1

2.1.1.1. Overall assessment

Pilot action evaluation summary

Specific objectives of the work package

The objective of WP1 is to provide the project with technical and administrative management, ensuring that it meets its technical objectives, deadlines, and milestones and that the deliverables are of high quality, meet the contractual obligations of the consortium, and are to the full satisfaction of all project partners and the EC.

Achievements and/or results

Organization of coordination meetings: Preparatory and KOM (01/2021), 1st Progress meeting and PMB meeting (03/2021), 2nd progress meeting and PMB meeting (05/2021).
Definition of the quality control procedure for the deliverables.

Problems/challenges faced

REA underwent a structural re-organization. Mr David Monteiro will no longer be part of the unit in charge of SWAFS. Ms Rinske van den Berg is the new project officer (comm. 23/04/2021).

Mr Julio García handed project coordination over to Ms Cecilia Soriano (accepted by the PO on 21/06/2021).

Implementation Status

Actors involved

CIMNE oversees project coordination. The partners are involved in the coordination tasks by leading the different work packages.

Methodology

The project's management procedures deal with four main aspects:

- 1) Operational management. This includes reporting to EC services and contacting them for administrative purposes, coordinating periodic reports, coordinating the final report, and resolving conflicts.
- 2) Financial management. This includes recording all costs incurred during the period, broken down by activity type; reporting costs to the EC; obtaining certificates of financial statements whenever needed; and transferring budget to the partners after payments by the EC.
- 3) Technical management. This concerns the monitoring of the project's scientific and technical progress. Technical management is implemented

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through four plenary meetings each year (in-person meetings at months 1 and 13, and two additional web meetings per year). The plenary technical meetings are complemented with web meetings addressing specific subjects as needed. Technical management also includes the definition of a quality assurance plan and project handbook for deliverables and software, monitoring of the project's research and scientific progress, and establishment of active collaboration with other initiatives in the same or related areas.

- 4) Legal and knowledge management. This includes the legal aspects of the project, such as negotiation and monitoring of the consortium agreement and definition of the intellectual property right regime.

CIMNE's experienced support staff is responsible for project administration and will aid in administrative and financial matters and take care of day-to-day management issues. The main coordination tools are the meetings. Technical issues are dealt with by means of progress meetings, in which all the researchers involved in the project are invited to participate.

The major decisions involved in the project are taken by the Project Management Board (PMB) made up of the project coordinator (acting as chairman) and one representative from each of the other project partners. PMB meetings are usually called in parallel to progress meetings to discuss the general guidelines and decisions on activities to be carried out by the project coordinator, work package leaders, and partners.

Plan Progress

This WP comprises the different activities related to the coordination required throughout the development of the project, such as communication with the Commission, management of the consortium, coordination of the PMB's management and technical meetings, and meeting preparation and post-processing activities (e.g., taking official minutes, ensuring that the project progresses according to the work plan).

Impact

Intended impact of actions and results

The impact of this WP relates to the outcomes and outputs of the prodPhD project. As the aim of this WP is to ensure the technical and administrative management of the project, its impact can be reflected by project outputs and outcomes in terms of communication, time, resources, and deliverables.

If actions completed, intended impact and comparison with actual impact of actions and results

Thus far, according to this deliverable (see conclusion), the intended impact of this WP is identical to its actual impact, which means that there is no urgent need for actions and/or deliberate interventions.

Modifications of the initial plan

No modifications of the initial plan were needed.

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2.1.1.2. KPI monitoring

This work package did not include any specific KPIs. However, an overall assessment of the monitoring of this work package's outputs and outcomes is provided in the section above.

2.1.2. Work Package 2

2.1.2.1. Overall assessment

Pilot action evaluation summary

Specific objectives of the work package

The main aim of this work package was to study and identify the needs and requirements of the target groups and to carry out a state-of-the-art analysis with a particular focus on offering entrepreneurship courses to PhD candidates.

Achievements and/or results

The work package identified the needs and requirements of the target groups. Two surveys were launched addressing the two target group segments (PhD candidates and faculty members) and were later combined with semi-structured interviews to contextualize the survey results [1]. The overall result of this work package was the identification of the needs and requirements of the target groups, so that the project's methodologies and content could be developed accordingly.

Problems/challenges faced

A key challenge in this work package was identifying the actual response rate to the PhD candidate survey. Initially, a purposive sampling technique was employed. The survey was sent to numerous institutions that later distributed the survey on their own platforms. The resulting network/snowball sampling technique blurred the actual number of PhD candidates to whom the survey was sent. Therefore, the actual response rate to the survey remained unknown.

Implementation Status

Actors involved

This work package was led by UC3M in collaboration with IPAG and WEGEMT.

Methodology

The work package consisted of two tasks. The first included a state-of-the-art analysis and the methodology, whereas the second included the execution of the surveys and interviews as well as an in-depth analysis thereof. Both tasks were drafted by the work package leader and were later reviewed and supplemented by the collaborating partners and the EAB. IPAG was involved in analysing some of the survey results, whereas WEGEMT was involved in the process of approaching the EAB and reviewers. Partner involvement was excellent and ensured that the tasks ran smoothly.

A mixed-instrument methodology was used in this work package to identify the needs and requirements of the target groups. The methods consisted of surveys and semi-structured interviews.

Gathered data

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In the first step, a literature review was conducted and a theoretical framework was fashioned. For this step data were gathered from existing literature sources, policy documents and policy briefs, and other European projects. In the following step an empirical analysis was carried out. In this analysis the data were gathered through two surveys and semi-structured qualitative interviews.

Plan Progress

There were two tasks in this work package. The first task was a preliminary report on the needs and requirements analysis. This task included the following activities:

- Literature review
- Theoretical framework
- Methodology
- Survey set-up

In the second task a final report was delivered that included the entire study of the needs and requirements analysis. This task included all the activities in the previous task plus:

- Data collection
- Survey of PhD candidates and faculty
- Semi-structured interview of PhD candidates and faculty
- Analysis
- Conclusions and recommendations
- Review processes

This work package was completed on August 31st, 2021. There are no tasks or activities remaining to be completed.

Impact

Intended impact of actions and results

The intended impact of the actions and results in this work package as a whole was the identification of the needs and requirements. However, the work package consisted of several activities, each with its own intended impact. For example, the surveys were intended to analyse what the target groups' goals were in taking and/or teaching entrepreneurship courses. The interviews' intended impact was to gather information to feed into the survey results and enrich the study with the target groups' qualitative views and perceptions. The intended impact of the study as a whole was pursued through these specific actions.

If actions completed, intended impact and comparison with actual impact of actions and results

There are no discrepancies between the activities' intended impact and actual impact. The actual impact matched the intended impact, which was to identify the needs and results of the target groups. This is demonstrated in the results of D2.2.

Modifications of the initial plan

Scheduled actions that were not performed, why?

Despite difficulties, all the scheduled actions were performed.

Actions that were modified, how?

None.

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Extra actions taken, why? Result?

An internal reviewing process among partners was one of the actions that was added in this work package. The reasons for these activities were, first, to ensure the soundness of the procedures and, second, to guarantee cohesion among the various work packages and/or pilot actions.

2.1.2.2. KPI monitoring

Code	Category	KPI	Target	Monitoring Dec 2021
P.PP1	Needs and requirements analysis	Adequacy/relevance of the materials collected	Qual	Very high
P.PP.3	Needs and requirements analysis	Sharing of answers to the survey on entrepreneurial teaching at the PhD level	>20%	35%*
P.PP.4	Needs and requirements analysis	Number of universities reached in the call for students (survey)	>30	60
P.PP.5	Needs and requirements analysis	Number of PhD programmes reached in the call for students (survey)	>50	44
P.PP.6	Needs and requirements analysis	Number of PhD students reached in the call for students	>300	111
P.PP.7	Needs and requirements analysis	Gender balance of the survey respondents	40-60%	46% female 54% male
P.PP.8	Needs and requirements analysis	Number of people interviewed/attending focus groups on entrepreneurial teaching at the PhD level	>7	10

* The share of answers to the survey was calculated with the universities' data (60 universities were reached and 21 responded), because due to the sampling method the partners do not have access to the exact number of students the survey reached.

2.1.3. Work Package 3

2.1.3.1. Overall assessment

Pilot action evaluation summary

Specific objectives of the work package

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This task aims at developing the social network-based methodology for teaching and learning entrepreneurship in PhD programmes. The methodology will be described in a set of guidelines that will define the structure, number, and goals of the modules of each training project.

Achievements and/or results

This WP presented the educational methodology aimed at providing PhD students with the necessary knowledge and skills to start and run their own business, be they aspiring or confirmed entrepreneurs.

Implementation Status

Actors involved

IPAG oversees this task, and the collaborating partner is UC3M.

Methodology

The entrepreneurship content is developed partly through the survey and in-depth interviews carried out in WP2 task T2.1 to identify PhD student and faculty needs and expectations.

- Among other findings, PhD student surveys and in-depth interviews show that a large majority of PhD students had not received any entrepreneurship training. They deemed instrumental skills – especially skills related with decision making, problem solving, leadership, and strategic planning – very valuable for entrepreneurship. They also thought that training should especially emphasize planning, resource procurement and management, product presentation and sales strategies, and examples of business success.
- Faculty members stated – among other viewpoints – that direct contact with entrepreneurs is a key point of entrepreneurship training. They particularly highlighted the development of skills such as the ability to bring a project/idea to the market, business plan development, and training for innovation and creativity.

The partners designed the entrepreneurship training programme for PhD students considering these conclusions. They supplemented these conclusions with their experience in entrepreneurship training for a large range of trainee types, from undergraduate and graduate students to professionals and aspiring entrepreneurs requiring vocational training.

Gathered data

This WP has built on the data provided by WP2 to set up the educational content to be used in the social network tools.

Plan Progress

This WP has been submitted for review. This WP has developed nineteen training modules based on the findings of WP2. The outcomes and outputs of this WP inform the activities of WP5 (demonstration actions). However, this deliverable is currently being reviewed by all partners involved to ensure further fine-tuning before the incorporation of the outcomes of WP3. After the integration of the necessary partner feedback, the outcomes of this WP will be used to proceed with WP5 (i.e., design of the demonstration actions and call for students).

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Impact

Intended impact of actions and results

The intended impact of the actions and results of this work package as a whole was to set up the educational methodologies to be used and exploited in WP5.

If actions completed, intended impact and comparison with actual impact of actions and results?

The outcomes of this WP are yet to be completed.

Modifications of the initial plan

No modifications of the initial plan were made.

2.1.3.2. KPI monitoring

Code	Category	KPI	Target	Monitoring Dec 2021
P.TD.1	Technical development	Number of training modules developed	8	19

2.1.4. Work Package 4

2.1.4.1. Overall assessment

Pilot action evaluation summary

Specific objectives of the work package

WP4, 'Development of the software tools and deployment of the social network platform', covers the activities required to design, develop, and deploy the software components of the prodPhD Online Training Environment. The goal of task 4.1 is to design the customized interface and the functionality of the prodPhD Online Training Environment, based on specifications defined from the analysis carried out in WP2. The work in this WP also includes the definition of a protocol for the comprehensive testing of the software environment and its components. This protocol will be used to perform a quality control of the software's functionality.

Achievements and/or results

To accomplish the requirements of WP4, Scipedia.com (an open science platform, www.scipedia.com) is being customized to provide the prodPhD Online Training Environment. The first step of customization is already finished. However, the final specifications of the training courses (to be defined in D3.1 'Guidelines of the training methodology and teaching and mentoring procedures', due by month 12) may make further adaptation necessary.

Scipedia.com offers the required social networking utilities as well as the possibility to create a virtual community (project) with its own personality (including a home page). The customized functionalities have been implemented on a microsite within Scipedia.com (https://www.scipedia.com?microsite_guid=246560).

The microsite enjoys the main capabilities of the open science platform, and its main components can be customized to fulfil specific requirements.

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The hosting microsite enables the prodPhD Online Training Environment to have:

- a customized layout and design,
- a dedicated URL,
- a project home page offering access to different contents,
- an overview of the prodPhD project,
- contact information and other social media information,
- profiles of the participating and collaborating organizations,
- news pages,
- links to open-access repositories for the different training materials, documents, and data,
- researcher profiles,
- analytics and statistics of the activity of the participants in the various actions.

Problems/challenges faced

The Online Training Environment is a framework where students can work collaboratively to prepare documents. The first challenge faced during the opening weeks of WP4 developments was the deployment of the project environment with its own personality and image, which differed from the Scipedia.com style.

Another main objective of WP4 is to deploy the software platform to be used in the development of the project's demonstration actions. A challenge to face is to provide students with short training courses (workshops) and to integrate the materials, documents, and data into this new paradigm of entrepreneurship training.

Implementation Status

Actors involved

The partner in charge of WP4, 'Development of the software tools and deployment of a Social Network platform', is CIMNE. WP4 has the following subtasks:

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WP / Task name
WP4. DEVELOPMENT OF SOFTWARE TOOLS AND DEPLOYMENT OF THE SOCIAL NETWORK PLATFORM
Task 4.1 Design of the software tools of the prodPhD Online Training Environment
Task 4.2 Customization of the software tools of the prodPhD Online Training Environment
Task 4.3 Development of a microsite in the platform Scipedia.com
Task 4.4 Deployment and tests of prodPhD Online Training Environment
Task 4.5 Training on the prodPhD Environment
M3: prodPhD Online Training Environment

Expected deliverables

No.	Name	WP	Leader	Type	D. Level	Delivery date
D4.1	prodPhD microsite at Scipedia.com	4	CIMNE	DEC	PU	M12
D4.2	prodPhD Online Training Environment	4	CIMNE	OTHER	PU	M18
D4.3	Documentation of the prodPhD Online Training Environment	4	CIMNE	R	PU	M18

CIMNE (and Scipedia as a third party involved in the project) prepared the 'prodPhD microsite at Scipedia.com' deliverable. During the early months of WP4, a microsite, https://www.scipedia.com?microsite_guid=246560, was built at Scipedia.com to host the prodPhD Online Training Environment.

All the tasks in WP4 performed during the period from January 2021 to December 2021 were carried out by CIMNE and Scipedia (as a third party). Tasks 4.1 'Design of the software tools of the prodPhD Online Training Environment' and 4.2 'Customization of the software tools of the prodPhD Online Training Environment' are currently in progress. The work to be done in those tasks depends on the specifications of the training courses, to be defined in D3.1 'Guidelines of the training methodology and teaching and mentoring procedures', which is due by month 12.

Task 4.3 'Development of a microsite in the platform Scipedia.com' is almost completed, and D4.1 will be delivered by month 12.

Tasks 4.4 (Deployment and test of prodPhD Online Training Environment) and 4.5 (Training on the prodPhD Environment), which start in M17, will involve the whole consortium to deploy the software platform to be used in the development of the demonstration actions and to offer two short training courses for the users of the prodPhD software environment.

Methodology

The prodPhD Online Training Environment allows the development of ‘learning by doing’ projects based on the methodology developed in the project. This methodology requires working groups and discussion forums, internal messaging, a document library, online collaborative edition tools, personal and community profiles, the project site, etc. These requirements (social network and collaborative work utilities) have not been built from scratch. Existing technology components of the open science platform Scipedia.com have been customized to provide a flexible, scalable solution to the project’s needs.

Gathered data

Data sources, data gathered (surveys, interviews, data from secondary sources, data from other work packages).

The design of the customized interface and the functionality of the prodPhD Online Training Environment are based on the specifications defined in the light of the analysis done in WP2. The work to be done in WP4 depends on the specifications of the training courses, to be defined in D3.1 ‘Guidelines of the training methodology and teaching and mentoring procedures’, which is due in month 12.

Plan Progress

The WP4 tasks started the second semester of 2021 with task 4.1 ‘Design of the software tools of the prodPhD Online Training Environment’, task 4.2 ‘Customization of the software tools of the prodPhD Online Training Environment’, and task 4.3 ‘Development of a microsite in the platform Scipedia.com’.

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WP / Task name	1st semester					2nd semester					3rd semester					4th semester							
	1	2	3	4	5	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
WP 4 DEVELOPMENT OF SOFTWARE TOOLS AND DEPLOYMENT OF THE SOCIAL NETWORK PLATFORM																							
Task 4.1 Design of the software tools of the prodPhD Online Training Environment																							
Task 4.2 Customization of the software tools of the prodPhD Online Training Environment																							
Task 4.3 Development of a microsite in the platform Scipedia.com																							
Task 4.4 Deployment and tests of prodPhD Online Training Environment																							
Task 4.5 Training on the prodPhD Environment																							

Task 4.1 and Task 4.2 are currently in progress. Task 4.1 ‘Design of the software tools of the prodPhD Online Training Environment’ will be completed in the upcoming weeks. Task 4.2 ‘Customization of the software tools of the prodPhD Online Training Environment’ will remain active throughout the whole duration of WP4.

Impact

Intended impact of actions and results

The prodPhD Online Training Environment has been designed as a flexible, scalable solution that can be adapted to a range of applications and is especially adaptable to the needs of the project’s ‘learn by doing’ requirements. It offers an integrated document and data management system, which enables specific repositories to be created and managed for the needs of the training exercises.

If actions completed, intended impact and comparison with actual impact of actions and results

Not available yet.

Modifications of the initial plan

No modifications have been made.

2.1.4.2. KPI monitoring

Code	Category	KPI	Target	Monitoring Dec 2021
P.TD.2	Technological development	Number of new features proposed (software tools, beta version)	>5	1

2.1.5. Work Package 5

2.1.5.1. Overall assessment

This WP is due to start in month 13. Therefore, since deliverable D6.2 reports project monitoring up to the 12-month point only, no WP5 evaluations or monitoring can be reported yet.

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2.1.5.2. KPI monitoring

Code	Category	KPI	Target	Monitoring Dec 2021
P.PP.1	Pilot phase	Level of engagement and types of stakeholders involved in the pilot action	Qual	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
P.PP.2	Pilot phase	Level of engagement and types of stakeholders involved in the implementation of the project outputs	Qual	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
P.PP.3	Pilot phase	Number of institutions involved in the call for the selection of interested PhD students	>30	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
P.PP.4	Pilot phase	Number of students reached in the call for the selection of interested PhD students	>100	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
P.PP.5	Pilot phase	Number of answers from PhD students reached in the call for the selection of interested students	>50	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
P.PP.6	Pilot phase	Number of PhD students involved in the demonstration actions	>30	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
P.PP.7	Pilot phase	Gender balance of the students involved in the demonstration actions	40 (60%)	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
P.PP.7	Pilot phase	Number of webinars during the project timeframe (students)	>2	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
P.PP.8	Pilot phase	Number of training modules considered adequate by the trainees	0.8	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
P.PP.9	Pilot phase	Number of training modules considered adequate by the trainers	0.8	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
P.PP.10	Pilot phase	Weaknesses identified through the PhD students involved in the pilot actions	Qual	To be evaluated in Dec 2022

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P.PP.11	Pilot phase	Strengths identified through the PhD students involved in the pilot actions	Qual	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
P.PP.12	Pilot phase	Assessment of the PhD students' report	Qual	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
P.FP.1	Final product	Adjustments to the methodological framework after consultation with stakeholders and target groups (workshop)	Qual	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
P.FP.2	Final product	Number of reported malfunctions solved (software tools, beta version)	All	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
P.FP.3	Final product	Number of new features implemented in the final release	>5	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
P.FP.4	Final product	Number of new features pending implementation in the final release	0	To be evaluated in Dec 2022

2.2. Output: dissemination and impact

2.2.1. Work Package 7

2.2.1.1. Overall assessment

Pilot action evaluation summary

Specific objectives of the work package

This WP will liaise both internally (with all prodPhD work packages) and externally (with stakeholders) to ensure that the project's best efforts and results are shared with the broadest possible audience. In addition, the goal of this task is to identify and engage with the relevant stakeholders to reach the objectives set out in the project and contribute to the widespread use of the resulting methodology and social network platform. Furthermore, the main goal of this task is to develop the dissemination and communication strategy. This will include specific messages and activities, content development, and a brand identity for the project's platform, website, and social media platforms.

Achievements and/or results

The key achievements/results so far include the following:

- The development of a comprehensive Engagement Strategy and a Communication, Dissemination and Outreach plan.
- The creation of a network of collaborating stakeholders (Expert Advisory Board (EAB) and collaborating projects), where 27 experts from 14 countries are currently participating (gender statistics: 26% female, 74% male). Eleven (11) of

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the registered experts have provided useful input to the ProdPhD work during the 1ST Workshop of the EAB which took place online on 20 October 2021. Many EAB members have also provided input to a number of ProdPhD deliverables throughout the 1st year of the project via e-mail. The coordinators of six (6) ProdPhD collaborating projects (BE OPEN, DIOSI, VERSA, SKIES, ISPAS and OPENING DOORS) are also members of the EAB and also participated in the 1st EAB workshop.

- Creation of ProdPhD social media accounts: LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/prodphd>) and Tweeter (<https://twitter.com/ProdPhD1>).
- All the dissemination activities have been measured against a set of KPIs developed under WP6. The results obtained so far show that four (4) out of ten (10) dissemination KPIs (O6, O7, O8 and O10) have been satisfied already, including the KPI **P.NR.2** “Number of collaborating organizations or enlisted in the Experts and Advisory Board EAB”). The remaining KPIs are monitored regularly and appropriate actions have been taken to make sure that they will be satisfied by the end of the ProdPhd project.

Challenges

The mobility restrictions imposed by the Covid-19 pandemic proved to be an obstacle as it limited the opportunities and ways of disseminating ProdPhD, and adversely affected all the offline tools and actions described in D7.2 (WP7): Communication, dissemination and outreach plan.

According to the plan of actions as described in the ProdPhD Grand Agreement, the main ProdPhD results are scheduled to be produced in the 2nd year of the project. So, the dissemination actions completed so far are limited to only raising awareness rather than disseminating and communicating results with the targeted audience-stakeholders.

Implementation Status

Actors involved

WEGEMT is the leader of WP7 and also leads two (2) out of its three (3) tasks, while CIMNE leads one task under WP7 and the other ProdPhD partners contributed, as shown in the table below.

Task No.	Deliverable	Responsible partner	Contributing partner	Due date	Status
T7.1	D7.1: Engagement strategy (type: Report)	WEGEMT	UC3M	M6	completed
T7.2	D7.2: Communication, dissemination and outreach plan (type: Report)	WEGEMT	CIMNE, UC3M, IPAG	M8	completed
T7.3	D7.3: Events (type: Report)	CIMNE	-	M3	completed

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Methodological steps

The methodology used in the work completed so far is based on a proactive approach and focused on the pertinent activities that are critical to the achievement of WP7 objectives, and consequently the objectives of prodPhD. The pertinent strategies were set at the beginning of the project and required the involvement/contribution of all the consortium partners.

Gathered data

The work done in WP7 so far has used input and feedback on the tasks under the active WP's from all consortium members, and also used feedback from the EAB members that was collected via direct communication and during the 1st EAB workshop of 20 October 2021.

Plan Progress

The work under WP7 is split into the following three tasks:

- a) Task 7.1: Conduct stakeholder analysis and engagement strategy
- b) Task 7.2: Communication, Dissemination and Outreach
- c) Task 7.3: Creation of the project website

Tasks 7.1 and 7.3 were completed in month 6 and month 4 respectively, while Task 7.2 is well in progress and is planned to last throughout the full duration of the project.

Impact

The actions completed so far under WP7 expect to have an impact related to the reinforcement of the network of ProdPhD stakeholders and raising their awareness about the key objectives and actions of the project.

Modifications of the initial plan

The offline tools and actions described in D7.2 (WP7): Communication, dissemination and outreach plan are affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, so they have not been performed.

Actions that were modified, how?

No actions have been modified at the moment.

Extra actions taken, why? Result?

The actions taken focus on identifying the appropriate mitigation actions to overcome the obstacles caused by the COVID-19 pandemic (i.e., use of a tight dissemination monitoring process, boost actions related to visibility of ProdPhD on the social media)

2.2.1.2. KPI monitoring

Code	Category	KPI	Target	Monitoring Dec2021
O.1	Dissemination	Number of scientific publications (peer- reviewed) submitted during the project	>4	0

O.2	Dissemination	Number of workshops organized (general)	≥2	1 (= the 1 st EAB workshop)
O.3	Dissemination	Number of people attending the meetings, training, local activities	>200	20 (=total people joined the 1 st EAB workshop)
O.4	Dissemination	Number of people, organizations, and stakeholders reached through dissemination, research, and training activities	>40	11 people, 11 organizations
O.5	Dissemination	Number of comments, shares, and retweets/reposts in social media	>250	65
O.6	Dissemination	Number of unique visitors to the project website	>200	759
O.7	Dissemination	Number of total sessions/visits to the project's website	>300	1425
O.8	Dissemination	Number of countries from which participants/readers come	>20	24
O.9	Dissemination	Average time spent on site/page	5 min	00:01:04
O.10	Dissemination	Number of visits and downloads of public documents from the website and open access repositories	100	1284

2.2.2. Work Package 8

2.2.2.1. Overall assessment

Pilot action evaluation summary

Specific objectives of the work package

The main goal of this WP is to develop a strategy based on an action plan to further develop the activities of the partnership beyond the project lifetime. In particular, it will explore potential synergies with policymakers and relevant stakeholders, along with plans for continued funding and for the possible development of diverse revenue streams.

Achievements and/or results

D8.1 has been delivered and is available on Scipedia. This document presents deliverable D8.1, the Data Management Plan (DMP) of work package 8 of the prodPhD project. The DMP is the plan for the management, generation, collection, security, preservation, and sharing of data generated through the prodPhD project. The DMP is a key element for organizing the project's data. It provides an analysis of the data collected, processed, and published by the prodPhD consortium.

The remaining two deliverables of this WP are due in month 24 of the project. Therefore, evaluations of these two deliverables will be included in the second project evaluation.

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Challenges

None

Implementation Status

Actors involved

IPAG oversees this work package. However, D8.1 was led by CIMNE. In addition to IPAG, CIMNE and UC3M are also collaborating on this work package.

Methodology

As the prodPhD project embraces European Commission initiatives to promote open access to research data, this deliverable follows open-access methodologies. Hence, to improve and maximize access to research data and their reuse, this deliverable bases its methodology on the principles of open access. Also, an open-access methodology implies that the collection of the data gathered throughout the prodPhD project as well as the outcomes (i.e., deliverables) are secure and accessible virtually over the project's microsite.

Gathered data

This WP gathers the data from the deliverables and pilot actions of the prodPhD project. Furthermore, the WP ensures open access to the data by ensuring that they are posted on the project's microsite.

Plan Progress

The DMP details what data the project will generate, whether and how the data will be made accessible for verification and re-use, and how the data will be curated and preserved. The progress plan calls for the creation of informed consent in D8.3 (due in month 24 of the project; to be appended to D8.1), a sustainability plan (D8.2), and an exploitation plan (D8.3).

Impact

Intended impact of actions and results

This WP facilitates and ensures the long-term impact of the prodPhD project. Thus far, D8.1 facilitates long-term impact by creating a data management plan and repository for the prodPhD project. Ensuring long-term impact will be discussed in D8.2 and D8.3, and their impact will be reported in the final term evaluation report.

If actions completed, intended impact and comparison with actual impact of actions and results

The actions of this WP have yet to be completed.

Modifications of the initial plan

No modifications of the initial plan.

2.2.2.2. KPI monitoring

This WP has no KPIs.

2.3. Overall Quality

2.3.1. Work Package 6

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2.3.1.1. Overall assessment

Pilot action evaluation summary

Specific objectives of the work package

The aim of this work package is to monitor and assess project development, impact, and results. The work package consists of three deliverables. The first task involved developing a landscape analysis and a methodological framework for monitoring and assessing the project's results and impacts. The second and third deliverables are initially similar; the only difference between them is the monitoring period. The second task aims to monitor the project's pilot actions twelve months after kick-off, whereas the third task aims to assess the project's pilot actions after 24 months.

Achievements and/or results

Thus far the first task (carrying out a landscape analysis and developing a methodological framework for monitoring and assessing the projects' results and impacts) has been completed [2]. In this task a preliminary set of KPIs was studied extensively. The validity and measurements of the indicators were evaluated and analysed. In a later step the deliverable was also reviewed by a panel of international experts.

Problems/challenges faced

Initially, the KPIs were not categorized or assigned to any specific pilot action(s). Indicator categorization and the assignment of the indicators to different activities presented some challenges. Also, the nature of the measurements was in some cases inadequate and posed some validity concerns. However, these challenges were turned into opportunities, which led to further specifications of some KPIs, the deletion of others, and the addition of new KPIs to ensure accurate monitoring.

Implementation Status

Actors involved

This work package was led by UC3M in collaboration with CIMNE and WEGEMT. The first task was led only by UC3M [2]. However, final report D6.1 was closely reviewed and evaluated by CIMNE. D6.2 is currently being implemented in collaboration with CIMNE, whereas D6.3 will be carried out in collaboration with WEGEMT and is due in December 2022.

Methodology

The D6.1 report relied on a pragmatic methodology. It aimed to ensure KPI accuracy for all partners involved. Therefore, it defined both the qualitative KPIs and the quantitative KPIs extensively. The definition of KPIs and their measurements were continuously discussed with the project partners.

Gathered data

The landscape analysis and the development of the methodological framework [2] relied on existing literature sources, drew on other European projects, and involved the experiences and perceptions of the project partners. The task was completed based on the data gathered through these sources.

Plan Progress

During the first twelve months of the project, the first task [2] was completed, and the second task was completed and submitted to the consortium. The last D6.3 task is due in December 2022.

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Impact

Intended impact of actions and results

The first task, D6.1 [2], was to perform a landscape analysis and develop a methodological framework to assess the set of preliminary KPIs. The task's intended impact was achieved by carrying out an extensive evaluation of the proposed KPIs. This evaluation led to the improvement of some definitions and measurements, the deletion of some KPIs, and the addition of new indicators.

If actions completed, intended impact and comparison with actual impact of actions and results

The intended impact of D6.1 was to reassess the proposed tasks. This reassessment included categorizing the indicators by their pilot phases and assigning them to different tasks and work packages. There are no disparities between intended impact and actual impact achieved.

Modifications of the initial plan

This WP has no modifications of the initial plan.

2.3.1.2. KPI monitoring

Code	Category	Category	Target	Monitoring Dec 2021
QA.M.1	Quality assessment	Number of timely answers from partners in consultation processes	>5	15
QA.M.2	Quality assessment	Number of KPIs proposed (qualitative, quantitative, long- and short-term)	>20	46
QA.M.3	Quality assessment	Number of KPIs enhanced after revision by the Expert Advisory Board (workshop)	>20	18
QA.M.4	Quality assessment	Share of KPIs successfully met	> 80%	To be evaluated in December 2022
QA.M.5	Quality assessment	Number of EAB consultations	>15	13
QA.M.6	Quality assessment	Number of meetings with the EAB	>3	1
QA.M.7	Quality assessment	Number of internal conflicts (consortium)	0	0

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QA.M.8	Quality assessment	Number of internal conflicts solved (consortium)	All	No conflicts
QA.M.9	Quality assessment	Transparency	Qual	Very high
QA.M.10	Quality assessment	Quality of the project's outputs	Qual	Very high
QA.SS.1	Quality assessment	Satisfaction of the PhD students involved in the demonstration activities	Qual	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
QA.SS.2	Quality assessment	Satisfaction of PhD students with the platform	Qual	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
QA.SS.3	Quality assessment	Feedback after consultation with stakeholders and target groups (workshop)	Qual	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
QA.SS.4	Quality assessment	Assessment and feedback from the Expert Advisory Board (EAB)	Qual	Very high
QA.TS.1	Quality assessment	Satisfaction of the working team involved in the development activities	Qual	To be evaluated in Dec 2022
QA.TS.2	Quality assessment	Satisfaction of the working team involved in the demonstration activities	Qual	To be evaluated in Dec 2022

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3. REFERENCES

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